

Structural Analysis of Knuckle Joint

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ABSTRACT - The knuckle joint serves as a crucial component in various mechanical systems, facilitating the connection between two rods while permitting angular movement under varying loads. This project focuses on the structural analysis of a knuckle joint to enhance its design efficiency and reliability. The study begins with a comprehensive examination of the geometric properties and material characteristics of the knuckle joint components, including the knuckle pin and fork. Utilizing finite element analysis (FEA) techniques, the project evaluates the joint's response to different loading conditions, encompassing axial loads, bending moments, and shear forces. The study investigates the influence of various design parameters, such as material selection, dimensions, and surface treatments, on the performance of the knuckle joint. This enables the identification of optimal design configurations that enhance strength, minimize weight, and optimize cost-effectiveness.

Keywords: knuckle joint, stress, strain, elastic strain, deformation

1. INTRODUCTION

A knuckle joint is a mechanical joint used to connect two rods which are under a tensile load, when there is a requirement of small amount of flexibility, or angular moment is necessary. There is always axial or linear line of action of load. The steering knuckle on your vehicle is a joint that allows the steering arm to turn the front wheels. The forces exerted on this assembly are of cyclic nature as the steering arm is turned to maneuver the vehicle to the left or to the right and to the centre again.

Steering knuckles come in all shapes and sizes. Their designs differ to fit all sorts of applications and suspension types. However, they can be divided into two main types. One comes with a hub and the other comes with a spindle. In this investigation, steering knuckle was used as a component for study. Mass or weight reduction is becoming an important issue in the car manufacturing industry. Weight reduction will give a substantial impact to fuel efficiency, efforts to reduce emissions and therefore, save the environment. Weight can be reduced through several types of technological improvements, such as advances in materials, design and analysis methods, fabrication processes and optimization techniques, etc. Steering Knuckle is subjected to time

varying loads during its service life, leading to fatigue failure. Therefore, its design is an important aspect in the product development cycle. Automotive makers continuously develop new vehicles with more luxury, convenience, performance, and safety. Often, they reduce vehicle weights which results in reduced energy consumption. A reduction in the weight of suspension components also improves the vehicle's handling performance. Therefore, design optimization should be implemented to obtain a minimum weight with maximum or feasible performance, based on conflicting constraints, design boundaries, and design uncertainties, such as design clearance and material defects. In his paper they studied the stresses in Knuckle joint using analytical method. Further study in this direction can be made by using various directions of the pin and the capacity to withstand load. The present work is concentrating on which type of meshing is preferable for components [1]. static analysis of steering knuckle component. The design of Steering Knuckle component is done with the help of Computer Aided Engineering (CAE). In this they have focused on optimizing the best use of material for the steering knuckle component and compare it, made from two materials i.e. Cast Iron and Mild Steel which is recently using, and Forge Steel EN 47 which is suggested material [2]. static analysis of steering knuckle. We have design a knuckle which accommodates dual caliper mountings for increasing braking efficiency & reducing a stopping distance of a vehicle. CAD model of knuckle was prepared in CREO 2.0. Static analysis was done in ANSYS WORKBENCH by constraining the knuckle, applying loads of braking torque on caliper mounting, longitudinal reaction due to traction, vertical reaction due to vehicle weight and steering reaction [3]. the steering knuckle in order to reduce the unsprung weight of a single seat All Terrain Vehicle (ATV) while retaining a satisfactory safety factor for better performance of the vehicle. A two-step process has been used for the same. First step is modelling the knuckle as per the structural considerations and design constraints set by suspension, steering and brake assemblies & determination of loads acting on the knuckle [4]. they reduced weight of the vehicle by increasing additional luxurious and safety features. The increasing weight of the vehicle affects the fuel efficiency and overall performance of the vehicle [5]. The aim of their research is to scale down the mass of an existing steering knuckle component of a local car model, using Creo 2.0, and performing its shape optimization, using Hyper works as pre and post processor and Nastran as a solver, in order to meet the required strength attributes at the cost of minimum weight [6]. they studied and calculated the stresses in Knuckle joint using analytical method. A knuckle joint is used to connect two rods

under tensile load. These joints are used for different types of connections e.g. tie rods, tension links in bridge structure. In this, one of the rods has an eye at the rod end and the other one is forked with eyes at both the legs [7]. they studies about steering and suspension system, which allows the front wheels to turn and also allow the movement of suspension arms motion. The light weight and high strength component is always in demanding for racecar application. Lightweight and optimized design of steering knuckle is proposed to use for a BAJA SAE INDIA off road racecar [8]. This can be achieved by performing a detailed load analysis. Therefore, this study has been dealt with two steps. First part of the study involves modeling of the steering knuckle with the design parameters using the latest modeling software, and also it includes the determination of loads acting on the steering knuckle as a function of time [9]. Optimized the steering knuckle targeting reducing weight as objective function with required strength and stiffness. In automotive suspension, a steering knuckle is that part which contains the wheel hub or spindle, and attaches to the suspension components. It is variously called a steering knuckle, spindle, upright or hub, as well [10]. To connect trailer to the tractor flexibly, a knuckle joint is used which consist of forks and a pin, a fork is attached to tractor rigidly and another fork is attached to the trailer by a pin. During acceleration of tractor, force acting on the joint is tensile and during deceleration it is compressive. Force acting over the joint is calculated by considering Newton's Second Law of motion [11]. . As per the functionality of the knuckle pin the pin is suitable for retaining of the knuckle and no loading conditions is determined over it but due to the manufacturability of the knuckle itself the failure of knuckle is undertaken thus the possible solution is presented in this thesis [12]. Many systems used in industries use knuckle joint which is combination of two materials: cast iron and stainless steel. Here we are proposing the modification of one of the material that is changing cast iron into a composite polymer material. The proposed system has many advantages over other system such as making the device, simpler and having maximum safety and is eco friendly [13].

II. METHODOLOGIES

CATIA (Computer Aided Three-dimensional Interactive Application) is a multi-platform CAD/CAM/CAE commercial software suite developed by the French company Assault Systems. Written in the C++ programming language, CATIA is the cornerstone of the Assault Systems product lifecycle management software suite.

1.1 Possible Failure Modes of Knuckle Joint

Tensile Failure of Rods:

Each rod is subjected to a tensile force P.

$$\text{Tensile stress in the rods} = \sigma_t = \frac{P}{\frac{\pi}{4}D^2} \leq [\sigma]$$

where $[\sigma]$ = allowable tensile stress for the material selected.

Shear Failure of Pin:

The pin is subjected to double shear as shown in Figure

Shear Stress in the pin,
$$\tau = \frac{P}{2 \left(\frac{\pi}{4} d^2 \right)} \leq [\tau]$$

Crushing Failure of Pin in Eye :

Projected Area of Pin in the eye = b d

Crushing Stress,
$$\sigma_{\text{crushing}} = \frac{P}{b d} \leq [\sigma_c]$$

where $[\sigma_c]$ = allowable compressive stress for the material selected.

Crushing Failure of Pin in Fork :

Projected Area of Pin in the fork = 2 a d

Crushing Stress,
$$\sigma_{\text{crushing}} = \frac{P}{2 a d} \leq [\sigma_c]$$

1.1.1 Bending Failure of Pin:

When the pin is tight in the eye and fork, failure occurs due to shear, but when it is loose, it is subjected to bending moment as shown in Figure . It is assumed that: Load acting on the pin is uniformly distributed in the eye and uniformly varying in the two parts of the fork.

Maximum Bending Stress in the pin,

$$\sigma_b = \frac{My}{I} \leq [\sigma]$$

1.1.2 Tensile Failure of Eye:

Area of the weakest section of eye resisting tensile failure = b (d₀ – d)

Maximum Tensile Stress in eye,

$$\sigma_t = \frac{P}{b (d_0 - d)} \leq [\sigma]$$

1.1.3 Shear Failure of Eye :

The eye is subjected to double shear

Maximum Shear Stress in eye =

$$\tau = \frac{P}{b (d_0 - d)} \leq [\tau]$$

Tensile Failure of Fork :

Area of the weakest section of fork resisting tensile failure = $2a (d_0 - d)$

Maximum Tensile Stress in fork =

$$\sigma_t = \frac{P}{2a (d_0 - d)} \leq [\sigma]$$

1.1.4 Shear Failure of Fork :

Each of the two parts of the fork is subjected to double shear.

Maximum Shear Stress in fork =
$$\tau = \frac{P}{2a (d_0 - d)} \leq [\tau]$$

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The main objective of this investigation is to do the structural analysis on knuckle joint with different materials at various loads and find out the behaviour of the knuckle joint at various

loads. Here in this analysis various factors were calculated by applying loads at appropriate sections of the knuckle joint.

Structural analysis was carried out on the Knuckle Joint at loads of 100N, 105N, 110N and 115N on three types of materials Stainless Steel, Bronze and Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymers and the action of various stress and strains on the knuckle joint at various loads were investigated.

Case -1: Investigation on Stainless Steel at various loads

❖ 1.1 At a load of 100N

Knuckle joint at 100N load

Total deformation in Knuckle joint at 100N

Here in this case the material used is stainless steel and the load acted upon the knuckle joint is about 100N and the structural analysis is done in order to find out total deformation in the knuckle joint. And the results were clearly shown in the figure. The above analysis was conducted on all parts of the knuckle joint and the results explain the same

Equivalent elastic strain

Here in this analysis also the material used, the geometries and the load are same as that of the above analysis, but in this analysis we calculated equivalent elastic strain under the structural analysis as we already know that the material chosen for this analysis has yield strength and so elastic strain can be calculated and the results of the elastic strain were shown in the figure.

Maximum principle stress

Here in this analysis also the material used, the geometries and the load are same as that of the above analysis, but in this analysis we calculated maximum principle stress under the structural analysis here after conducting structural analysis we got maximum principle stress of about 0.0301MPa and a minimum of -0.0188 MPa and that were clearly shown in the figure.

Maximum shear stress

Here in this analysis also the material used, the geometries and the load are same as that of the above analysis, but in this analysis we calculated maximum shear stress under the structural analysis here after conducting structural analysis we got maximum shear stress of about 0.0468 MPa and a minimum of 0.0252MPa and that were clearly shown in the figure.

Equivalent von-mises stress

Here in this analysis also the material used, the geometries and the load are same as that of the above analysis, but in this analysis we calculated equivalent Von-Mises stress under the structural analysis here after conducting structural analysis we got maximum shear stress of about 0.0888 MPa and a minimum of 0.009 MPa and that were clearly shown in the figure here the maximum load is obtained at fixed supports

IV. CONCLUSION

The knuckle component has been modeled using CATIA and analyzed using ANSYS WORKBENCH 2024 R1. The various parameters such as total deformation, Shear stress, Equivalent stress, And Maximum Shear Stress are completely analyzed. This analysis represent that the areas where the stress concentration is maximum due to the applied load of 100KN, 105 KN, 110 KN, 115 KN. The study of knuckle component gives the small change in directional deformation and reduced the overall weight of vehicles due to decrease in weight of steering knuckle component as well as save the materials and cost and improved the vehicles performance.

The comparison between Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers (CFRP) and Bronze for the manufacturing of knuckle joints reveals significant differences in material properties and suitability for specific applications. CFRP demonstrates superior mechanical properties, including higher equivalent stress and equivalent elastic strain, indicating greater strength and stiffness compared to Bronze.

This suggests that knuckle joints made from CFRP are better equipped to withstand higher loads without experiencing excessive deformation. However, it's important to consider the cost and manufacturing considerations associated with CFRP, which may involve higher production costs and specialized equipment.

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